

The Barreto’s Mars Tessellation as a Variable Radiative Heat Transfer Device

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Abstract

Variable Radiative Heat Transfer Devices (VRD) exhibit dynamic variation of radiative heat transfer through modifications to surface properties or emitting geometry. Origami tessellations provide a means by which both radiative surface properties and emitting geometry might be controlled in real time. The Barreto’s Mars tessellation is an especially interesting fold for application as a VRD, collapsing to a finite surface area. Optimization routines, combined with Monte Carlo ray tracing, were used to identify Barreto’s Mars designs that satisfy two separate objective functions. A sequential quadratic programming algorithm was applied to a second-order polynomial surrogate model of the ray tracing results to find the optimal solution for two objective problems with variable weights. Optimization through the Nelder-Mead simplex was performed to confirm the results. The largest change in apparent emissivity during the devices actuation occurred when all panels were very reflective with purely specular reflection, and when all panels were rectangular with a 3:1 length-to-width ratio. Likewise, the smallest change in projected surface area over actuation, or the configuration that requires the least amount of material while still considering a large change in apparent emissivity, had the same configuration except panel set 1 had an emissivity of .38 and panel set 2 had a minimal interior angle.

1 Introduction

In environments dominated by radiation heat transfer, thermal control systems must employ creative techniques to maintain component temperatures within an acceptable range. As an example, consider a spacecraft in Low Earth Orbit (LEO). Variations in solar irradiation, albedo irradiation and spacecraft

operating power generate a wide range of possible heat loads, ranging from near zero to some maximum value [1]. However, the factors that control radiative heat loss from the spacecraft are relatively constant values, prohibiting the ability to dynamically control spacecraft heat loss to the environment. To account for unwarranted heat loss, satellite thermal systems incorporate the use of thin film heaters to maintain critical components within a given temperature range [1, 2]. Although effective, this thermal control methodology accounts for approximately 10% [1] of the spacecraft’s power budget and requires additional solar panels and battery space to be placed on board.

Similar thermal control methodology is found in other radiation heat transfer dominated applications. Domestic structures are exposed to significant variation in solar irradiation over a 24 hour period. Likewise, this variation in solar irradiation changes throughout the calendar year. To account for this variation in heat load, the environment within the structure is conditioned through heating or air conditioning, consuming significant amounts of power in the process. In 2011, 48% of all domestic power usage went towards heating or cooling of the structures internal environment [3].

A more efficient thermal control methodology would control the total heat loss from the system as a function of the thermal environment and heating conditions to maintain a relatively isothermal system. NASA has identified the ability to vary heat rejection from a satellite as “the most critical thermal technology development.” [4] Variable Radiative Heat Transfer Devices (VRD’s) provide this capability, creating variations in radiative losses through modifications to radiative surface properties or emitting geometry in real time. Currently, the majority of VRD’s are electrochromic or thermochromic sur-

(a) The accordion or "v-groove" tessellation. As these folds are actuated, cavities develop in the surface, increasing the emissivity of the cavity openings. However, the decrease in emitting surface area causes the total heat transfer to approach zero as the surface is actuated.

(b) The behavior of apparent emissivity (Equation 1), opening surface area and total heat transfer for an infinite V-groove, a close approximation of the accordion fold. The radiative heat transition is proportional to the product of apparent emissivity and opening surface area, as shown in Equation 2.

Figure 1: The accordion tessellation and how the apparent emissivity and cavity opening area impact the radiative heat transfer from the tessellation.

face coatings. Electrochromics undergo a reversible redox reaction in the presence of a voltage difference, with increases in emissivity ranging from 0.6 to 0.8 [5–9]. Thermochromic coatings, mostly variations of Vanadium Oxide (VO_2), transition from a semi-conductor state to a metal state at a given temperature with an accompanying change in radiative surface properties [10–12]. Surface geometry modifications likewise accomplish a change in radiative heat loss, with devices utilizing both microscale [13, 14] and macroscale [15–17] geometry modifications.

A new device [18, 19] proposes the use of origami tessellations as a means of controlling radiative heat transfer. As a tessellation is actuated from an open to a closed state, cavities develop. Increased interreflections within these cavities augment the emission from the surface opening in a phenomenon known as the cavity effect. The apparent emissivity of the cavity, defined in Equation 1, measures the emission of the cavity opening as compared to a black surface, where E_{cavity} is the total emission from the cavity opening and E_{black} is the emission from an equivalent cavity with an intrinsic emissivity of unity. This factor is a function of the cavity geometry and cavity radiative properties. Because the tessellation geometry is directly related to the apparent emissivity of the inherent cavities, origami tessellations present a viable method by which radiative properties and heat transfer (Equation 2) might be controlled.

$$\epsilon_a = E_{cavity}/E_{black} \quad (1)$$

$$q_{net,rad} = \epsilon_a A_{opening} \sigma T_s^4 \quad (2)$$

For many origami tessellations, such as the simple accordion fold, shown in Figure 1a or Miura-Ori tessellation [20], the emitting surface area of the tessellation decreases as the surface is collapsed, approaching a value of zero. Despite the increasing apparent emissivity, the net effect is a reduction in heat transfer as the tessellation is collapsed, with the total heat transfer decreasing towards zero as the tessellation assumes its fully compressed state (Figure 1b). Although these tessellations are still functional, an ideal VRD would not decrease to a state of negligible heat transfer. One tessellation capable of such behavior is the Barreto’s Mars.

The Barreto’s Mars tessellation [21] is a relatively new tessellation with some interesting characteristics. As shown in Figure 2, the tessellation assumes a flat state at both the beginning and ending of its actuation path, with cavities developed over the course of the actuation. The relative sizes of the beginning and ending emitting areas and the behavior of the apparent emissivity of the cavity with respect to actuation position are functions of several tessellation design parameters, pictured in Figure 2. These terms include the fold angles α and β , the ratio of side lengths A and B , the actuation position ϕ , the intrinsic emissivities ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 and qualities Q_1 and Q_2 of panels 1 and 3 and panels 2 and 4, respectively. The quality is a ratio of energy reflected diffusely compared to the total energy reflected, allowing for the reflection mode of the panels to be varied from perfectly specular (a

Figure 2: The Barreto’s Mars geometry, illustrating the unique ability of this tessellation to collapse to a finite emitting area and defining the design variables that will be utilized in this optimization.

quality of 0) to perfectly diffuse (a quality of unity).

In practice, the ideal origami radiator design would produce the largest possible change in heat transfer over the actuation cycle. Likewise, the amount of material would be minimized to decrease the weight of the technology. The purpose of this work is to search the design space of the Barreto’s Mars (α , β , ϕ , A/B , ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , Q_1 and Q_2 as design variables) to find the combination of design variables that produces the largest change in apparent emissivity as the device is actuated while minimizing the weight by maximizing the change in projected surface area over the complete actuation the device. The apparent emissivity will be determined using a ray tracing algorithm and the optimal value of the weighted objective functions will be determined using both the Nelder-Mead Simplex and Sequential Linear Programming of a surrogate model.

2 Methodology

In order to optimize either the apparent emissivity of the tessellation or the required material of the device, a model predicting these value as a function of the design variables is necessary. A standard radiative heat transfer resistance model is insufficient in this situation owing to the non-uniform distribution of radiosity across the tessellation panels [22]. As such, Monte Carlo ray tracing was used to approximate the heat transfer.

2.1 Monte Carlo Ray Tracing

Monte Carlo ray tracing is a numeric experiment used to predict radiation heat transfer between surfaces and is well-suited for analysis of complicated geometries. Excellent reviews by Prokhorov [23, 24] and Sapritsky [25] summarize the approach and details associated with Monte Carlo ray tracing. In summary, a large quantity of rays is emitted at random directions from random locations on a given geometry and the path of these rays is tracked through space. Upon intersecting other parts of the geometry, the rays are reflected or absorbed according to the material’s radiative surface properties. Some rays will leave the geometry without being absorbed while other rays will be absorbed. The resulting ratio of escaped to emitted rays may be used to derive the apparent emissivity of the surface, as shown in the following derivation.

Figure 3 depicts an emitting tessellation, with a control volume drawn to include the entirety of the tessellation, including the emitting and absorbing walls. A given quantity of energy, Q_{total} , is emitted from the cavity walls, a portion of which, $Q_{absorbed}$, is absorbed. The remainder, Q_{escape} , leaves the cavity opening. The total emission and escaped energies may be expressed as Equations 3 and 4, allowing for variation in the panel emissivities, where $A_{emit,i}$ is equivalent to the total surface area of the panels of

the tessellation with emissivity ϵ_i .

$$Q_{total} = \epsilon_1 \sigma A_{emit,1} T^4 + \epsilon_2 \sigma A_{emit,2} T^4 \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{escape} = \epsilon_a \sigma A_{opening} T^4 \quad (4)$$

Combining these equations with an energy balance of the control volume and solving for apparent emissivity gives Equation 5 after simplification.

$$\epsilon_a = \left(\frac{\epsilon_1 A_{emit,1} + \epsilon_2 A_{emit,2}}{A_{opening}} \right) - \frac{Q_{absorbed}}{\sigma T^4 A_{opening}} \quad (5)$$

Equation 3 is then used to redefine σT^4 in Equation 5. After simplification and utilizing the total energy balance $Q_{total} = Q_{absorbed} + Q_{escaped}$, the apparent emissivity may be defined as given in the middle portion of Equation 6. It is now necessary to draw an analogy between heat transfer and ray tracing results, being that a ray behaves in a similar manner to a photon [26]. Given this equivalence, the ratio of energy escaped to energy emitted is equivalent to the ratio of rays escaped to rays emitted, giving the apparent emissivity as a function of ray tracing results in Equation 6.

$$\epsilon_a = \frac{N_{escape}}{N_{total}} \frac{\epsilon_1 A_{emit,1} + \epsilon_2 A_{emit,2}}{A_{opening}} \quad (6)$$

A custom ray tracing program has been developed, using the Java programming language, to determine the apparent emissivity and heat transfer of origami tessellations. The geometry to be analyzed is imported into the program as a series of surfaces with radiative properties and reflection mode assigned to each surface. Sets of random numbers are used to generate the location and emission direction of each ray, with the number of rays per unit area defined by the user. Each ray is then individually tracked, and a point of intersection with another surface (if an intersection exists) is calculated. A series of random numbers is used to determine if the ray is reflected, and in which direction it is reflected [27]. The program counts the total number of rays emitted and the number of rays that escape from the surface without being absorbed. Given the large number of computations necessary, a typical ray trace of the Barretto's Mars tessellation required approximately three seconds at 250,000 rays.

2.2 Geometry

The Barretto's Mars tessellation consists of a four-panel vertex and its inversion [21]. The tessellation, which is rigidly-foldable, is a repeating pattern of the vertex, mirrored on each iteration. Each repeated

Figure 3: The control volume used to derive apparent emissivity, Equation 6. The terms $Q_{escaped}$ and $Q_{absorbed}$ include energy that was reflected multiple times before being absorbed or escaping the tessellation.

pattern maintains equal actuation angle (ϕ) magnitudes across the entire tessellation. The pattern can reach a flat state without intersection of the panels.

The geometry was simulated by creating vectors associated with the input variables; specifically α , β , ϕ , and A/B . A basic geometry unit was established as simply a base parallelogram, the adjacent quadrilateral, and the mirrored, rotated inversion of the two, unrepeated. The two base parallelograms could be defined algebraically with the two fold angles α and β , and with the ratio A/B . The mirrored pattern was then approximated by creating a system of linear equations relying on the actuation angle ϕ . In this work, panel set 1 is defined as the darker panel, and panel set 2 is the lighter panel on the right in Figure 2.

When α is less than β , the top half of the geometry collapses in towards the same direction as ϕ . However, when α is greater than β , the top half folds out and away from ϕ lest the faces intersect in a physically impossible manner. This interaction was included amongst our constraints. To simplify the model, α was constrained to be less than 90° , which is less than β , bounded between 90° and 180° . This ensured the geometry would behave consistently and collapse in on itself.

2.3 Objectives and Constraints

With a mechanism in place to describe apparent emissivity as a function of design variables, an optimization of the objectives posed in Section 1 is now possible. These statements, and their physical constraints, must first be described mathematically.

2.3.1 Objective Functions

The first objective seeks the largest change in apparent emissivity over actuation (variation in ϕ). Equation 7 gives the basic interpretation of this statement. The term $\epsilon_{a,max}$ must be determined through use of the ray tracing algorithm. $\epsilon_{a,min}$, however, will always occur at the flat state ($\phi = 180^\circ$) and may be defined by Equation 6 at an angle of $\phi = 180^\circ$.

$$J_1(x) = \epsilon_{a,max} - \epsilon_{a,min} \quad (7)$$

For the second objective function, the total collapsed area exposed to the surroundings as compared to the total surface area of the flat tessellation is maximized. This objective is quantified in Equation 8, where A_{total} is the total amount of emitting surface area present in the tessellation and $A_{opening_collapsed}$ corresponds to the surface area of the tessellation exposed to the surroundings when fully closed. This closed area does not include those portions of the collapsed unit cell that would be covered by other unit cells when included in a repeating tessellation.

$$J_2(x) = \frac{A_{opening_collapsed}}{A_{total}} \quad (8)$$

Both objective functions were optimized simultaneously using a weighting parameter W , as given in Equation 9. The weighting parameter was varied from the lowest value of 0.2 to the highest value of 10 as a means of exploring the design space. The optimal values will allow for the creation of a Pareto Front, illustrating the interaction between both objective functions.

$$J(x) = J_1(x) + WJ_2(x) \quad (9)$$

2.3.2 Constraints

The majority of constraints governing this problem are upper and lower bounds and are derived from the physical limitations of each design variable. Table 1 lists these bound constraints. The emissivity and quality values are restricted to values between zero and unity due to their definitions. In terms of geometry, the angles α and β are linked, where α cannot exceed β without changing the behavior of the geometry. The violation of these requirements would cause the creases of the tessellation to fold in the opposite direction, effectively creating a new tessellation that is beyond the scope of this work. Specifically, α was bound between 1° and 89° , while β was constrained between 90° and 179° . ϕ is likewise limited to restrict the actuation between fully expanded and fully collapsed. Finally, the limits on A/B were selected to keep the final design within a reasonable bound.

Table 1: The constraints associated with the objective functions given in Section 2.3.1. All angle constraints are provided in degrees, but were implemented using radians. Two values are provided for each bound constraint. The first value indicates the bounds that were used to generate training and validation data for the surrogate model. The second value indicates the constraints actually utilized in optimizing the objective functions.

Design Variable	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
ϵ_1	0.0 / 0.1	1.0 / 0.9
ϵ_2	0.0 / 0.1	1.0 / 0.9
ϕ	1° / 5°	179° / 170°
α	1° / 30°	89° / 89°
β	90° / 90°	179° / 150°
A/B	0.25 / 0.5	4.00 / 3.00
Q_1	0.0 / 0.0	1.0 / 1.0
Q_2	0.0 / 0.0	1.0 / 1.0

2.4 Optimization

Noise was present in the ray tracing results due to the stochastic nature of the Monte Carlo process. Results could be made more repeatable by increasing the total number of rays, but this increased the total time required to make a function call and did not eliminate the noise entirely. An attempt was made to maintain the random number set used throughout the ray tracing algorithm, smoothing the gradients between function calls. However, attempts to do so proved futile and time-consuming as the algorithm was created to allow for multi-core processing, complicating the matter beyond our abilities. As such, the net effect of this uncertainty was the inability to determine an accurate function gradient. With function gradients inaccessible, gradient-free optimization methods had to be utilized.

2.4.1 Surrogate Model

A surrogate model entails the creation of a representative function to approximate the behavior of the objective to be optimized [28]. Many types of surrogate models exist, from the simple linear regression to the complicated and reliable neural network. For this work, a second-order polynomial regression was utilized including all interactions between every design variable.

Five hundred data points were generated using latin-hypercube sampling distributed over a beta distribution with weighting parameters (0.01, 0.01). This created a data sample that was weighted to-

(a) Apparent emissivity curves of the surrogate model for four different intrinsic emissivities of both panel set 1 and 2. A maximum is clearly evident in all cases in the region of 50° . Objective 1 seeks to maximize the difference between the maximum and minimum apparent emissivity values for a given set of design variables.

(b) The fully open and fully closed (shadowed) geometries of one unit cell. When multiple unit cells are combined into a tessellation, only the blue portions of the closed geometry are open to the environment and thus emitting heat to the environment. Objective 2 seeks to maximize the closed-geometry area that is exposed to the surroundings, normalized by the total surface area of the open configuration.

Figure 4: Physical descriptions of the two objective functions that are to be optimized in Equation 9

wards the bounds of the problem as this is where the optimum exists, increasing the model’s accuracy in that region. An additional five hundred points were created to validate the model upon its creation, following a similar distribution. The model was created using the standard linear regression matrix multiplication method [28]. The surrogate model was fit to Equation 7. Attempts to fit other values, such as N_{escape}/N_{total} or ϵ_a , proved less accurate and yielded optimal design variables that were known to be incorrect.

Upon the creation of the surrogate model, the overall objective function, Equation 9, was optimized using Sequential Quadratic Programming [29]. When an optimal point was determined, the result (Equation 9) of the surrogate model at the optimal point was compared with the result of the ray tracing algorithm. If the resulting values were not within 10%, normalized with respect to the ray tracing results, 10 additional data points were generated within the region of the optimal value and the surrogate model was regenerated. The objective was optimized again, and this pattern repeated until the resulting values were within the tolerance specified. This routine was performed for weighting parameters ranging from 0.05 to 10.

As shown in Table 1, the actual bounds used to optimize the objective function were not the same as those used to generate the surrogate model training and validation data. In performing the optimization,

it was found that the surrogate model was especially inaccurate in the ‘corners’ of the design space, where all bounds were active. The surrogate model often converged to these locations and additional infilling procedures did not improve the model’s predictions at these points. As such, the optimization bounds were restricted so as to allow for the model to remain fairly accurate over the design space.

2.4.2 Nelder-Mead Simplex

As the surrogate model is not exact, the Nelder-Mead simplex [29] was used to validate the result for a select number of weighting parameters. The design variables were modified using the quadratic penalty method to ensure adherence to the bound constraints. If the result of the Nelder-Mead optimization was not within 5% of the surrogate model optimized value, the entire optimization process was repeated for that weighting parameter. The Nelder-Mead was not used as the primary optimization method because the number of function calls to convergence was large and the routine often converged to locations in the design space that were not actual minimums.

3 Results

3.1 Surrogate Model

The initial surrogate model reported an R^2 value of 0.70 and a root mean square error of 0.08 when evaluated with the validation data set, giving about 20% normalized error on average. The largest discrepancy for a single data point was 40%. However, It should be noted that these statistics include the expanded bounds, whereas the optimization was performed within the more restricted bounds were the model was shown to be more accurate. Depending on the weighting parameter and design variable set, between two and six infilling procedures were necessary to bring the surrogate model and ray tracer to within 10% agreement.

Figure 5: A comparison of the surrogate model and actual data of apparent emissivity data over the full actuation of a Barreto’s Mars tessellation with $\alpha = 45^\circ$, $\beta = 90^\circ$, $A/B = 1$, and $\epsilon = 0.4$, $Q = 0$. The behavior is not entirely captured by the second-order polynomial model, but the maximum and minimum are in the correct locations for both data sets.

Figure 5 shows a comparison between the surrogate model and ray tracing results for the geometry depicted in Figure 2 with panel emissivities of 0.4. Clearly, a second-order polynomial model is not sufficient to correctly predict the function value at all actuation positions. However, the maximum and minimum apparent emissivity locations are predicted correctly by the surrogate model. This maximum accuracy was found to exist in all cases that were compared, suggesting that the surrogate model is well-suited for the optimization of Objective 1.

3.2 Optimization

The objective function with a given weighting parameter ($0.05 < W < 10$) was optimized a minimum of 5 times at random starting points, allowing for the infilling procedure to come to convergence for each optimal value. A total of 35 different weighting parameters between the weight parameter bounds were explored in this study, with an increased number of weighting values resulting in greater resolution near the value of $W = 2$. Table 2 provides the optimal set of design variables as a function of weighting parameter. Two distinct solutions exist, with a weighting value of 1.88 separating the two optimal design variable sets. Several local minimum were reported by the optimizer for a variety of starting points and weighting values, but a simple comparison of objective function values at each returned optimal point served to identify the global optimum. The Pareto Front that results from this weighting study consists simply of two points, corresponding to the two unique solutions, and as such is not provided in plotted form.

4 Discussion

The first design variable solution set, which has been optimized with weighting values that bias the solution towards Objective 1, is an intuitive solution. The cavity effect is strongest (and therefore the change in ϵ_a is largest) for deeper cavities. α and β have assumed values such that the surface is composed of four approximate rectangles which fold up rapidly with actuation angle. The resulting cavity is the deepest cavity possible. Likewise, changes in ϵ_a are augmented by specularly-reflecting, highly-reflective surfaces. The first optimal solution determined that the design variables ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , Q_1 and Q_2 should be 0.1 and 0.0, or very reflective and having purely specular reflection. This selection by the optimizer further validates the solution. Finally, especially for highly-reflective surfaces, ϵ_a continues to increase as the surface is collapsed, validating the existence of the ϵ_a maximum at a ϕ of 10° , the lower bound of that design variable. The solution was consistent in selecting deeper cavities, although the exact physical reasoning for this selection is currently unclear.

The second solution proved more interesting. This solution was the optimal value when the weighting function emphasized the need to limit the reduction in area nearly twice as much as the need to drive up the change in apparent emissivity. As such, α switches from activating the upper bound of its constraint to the lower bound of its constraint, making

Table 2: The optimal design variables for given weighting values. Instead of developing a continuous Pareto Front, variation in the weighting parameter only revealed two distinct solutions.

Weight	ϵ_1	ϵ_2	Q_1	Q_2	β	α	A/B	ϕ
0.05 - 1.88	0.1	0.1	0	0	90°	89°	3	10°
1.88 - 10	0.38	0.1	0	0	90°	30°	3	60°

panel set 2 as small as possible, preventing panel set 2 from covering most of panel set 1. Once objective 2 was optimized, the remaining parameters were varied until the largest change in apparent emissivity was found for the given geometry parameters. This is what drives the selection of an emissivity of 0.38 for panel set 1. As this panel set is the larger of the two, selecting a higher emissivity allows the surface to emit more radiation which now has a higher probability of being intersected by the smaller panel set 2. Likewise, panel set 2 is made as reflective as possible so as to reflect the majority of the heat away, augmenting the cavity effect.

The existence of only two discrete solutions was unexpected. Additional resolution in the weighing value did not deliver any new optimums. Each optimal value represents the exact solution to one or the other of the single objective functions, suggesting that the weighting function is not performing properly. However, the average error of the surrogate model was on the order of the solution to Objective 1 for the second optimal design parameter set, suggesting that a more accurate surrogate model may be necessary to determine the real optimal values near the region of $W = 1.88$, creating a continuous Pareto Front. Additionally, Objective 1 is a function of all of the design variables, whereas Objective 2 is a function of only α , β and A/B . This variation in variable dependence could also be driving the Pareto Front towards two discrete solutions.

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